

Style for *IRRN* Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*; Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.
- Type all contributions double-spaced. ¶

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

RxT-42 or Himdhan, a new, stable, high yielding rice for hilly areas of Himachal Pradesh, India

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Himachal Pradesh (H.P.) is a hilly state with undulating topography and diverse agroclimate conditions that range from subtropical to temperate. In the kharif season, rice is an important crop. It occupies 100,000 ha and is cultivated at altitudes as high as 2,290 m.

Many rice varieties are needed for H.P.'s diverse agroclimatic conditions. Most recommended varieties – including IR579, the recently recommended high yielding variety with good grain quality – are suitable for areas up to 1,070 m. Norin 18 and Norin 8, japonica types recommended for high-altitude areas between 915 and 1,370 m, are not popular with farmers because of their coarse grain and poor cooking quality. China 988 with medium-coarse grain is the only variety that can be cultivated from the plains up to an altitude of 1,525 m. It is the most widely grown recommended variety, but it is susceptible to blast disease and lodging, and needs to be replaced.

The experimental line RxT-42 consistently performed well and outyielded China 988, Norin 18, and IR579 in the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) and H. P. University trials from 1970–76. Its overall yield, based on 25 AICRIP trials, was 4.1 t/ha, an increase of about 13% over that for China 988 (3.6 t/ha) (see table). In yearly trials, RxT-42 outyielded China 988 by 5.4 to 28.4%.

Yield stability parameters for 20 rices tested in the Elite Varieties Trials (EVT) during 1975 and 1976 in 14 environments, at elevations ranging from 308 to 1,371 m, indicated that RxT-42

Overall mean yield of RxT-42 and China 988 from 1970 to 1976. Himachal Pradesh, India.

Year	No. of locations	Average yield (t/ha)	
		RxT-42	China 988
1910	1	6.3	4.9
1911	5	5.1	4.2
1912	2	4.2	3.9
1913	10	5.1	4.3
1914	1	4.1	3.1
1915	10	3.6	3.4
1916	33	3.1	3.4
Mean		4.1	3.6

had average performance (mean yield, 2.4 kg per 2 × 3-m plot) and high stability (regression, 0.87 and deviation from regression, 0.016). It yielded significantly higher than China 988.

RxT-42 can easily replace China 988 at elevations of up to 1,370 m in H.P. and other hilly areas of India, and has recently been recommended to the State Variety Release Committee for release under the name Himdhan. The AICRIP Annual Workshop also recommended it for release in H.P. in April 1977.

RxT-42 is a progeny of the cross R-575/TN1. R-575 is a purple-leaved, tall, stiff-strawed, and blast-resistant local recommended variety. RxT-42 matures only 2 to 4 days later than China 988 and has more spikelets per panicle and higher test weight. ¶

Breeding methods used in 10 Asian nations

Thomas R. Hargrove, associate editor, International Rice Research Institute

As part of an IRRI study of rice breeding programs in Asia, a survey was made of the breeding methods used in hybridization programs by 31 rice breeders at 24 research centers in 10 Asian countries. The project, initiated in 1975, was partially funded by a research grant from the Rockefeller Foundation.

The breeding methods used by 31 rice breeders at 24 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian countries, 1975.

Breeding method	1st		2nd		Choice of method				Users ^a	
	no.	%	no.	%	3rd		4th		no.	%
Pedigree	21	68	3	10	3	10	2	6	29	94
Backcross	2	6	10	32	5	16	2	6	19	60
Bulk	1	3	9	29	5	16	0	0	15	48
Mutation ^b	0	0	3	10	4	13	5	16	12	39
Combination	6	19	3	10	5	16	4	13	18	58
Others	1	3	1	3	5	16	1	3	8	26
No indication	0	0	2	6	4	13	17	55	—	—

^aThe number and percentage of 31 breeders who indicated that they used each method as at least one of their breeding systems.

^bChemical, radiation, or natural.

Sixty-eight percent of the breeders (21) depended primarily on the pedigree method of breeding (see table); two breeders depended mostly on the backcross method, and one on the bulk method. Six breeders (19%) indicated that they depended primarily on a combination of breeding techniques.

Ninety-four percent of all breeders

surveyed used the pedigree system (in combination with other methods); 60% used the backcross method; and 48%, the bulk system.

Although none of the breeders depended primarily on mutation breeding (chemical, radiation, or natural) in their programs, 39% used mutation in combination with other methods.

ARC 11775 — an Assam rice cultivar that is promising for rainfed lowlands

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Kerala state grows 395,000 ha of monsoon rice. More than 80% of the area under autumn rice is sown in dry soil in mid-April during the premonsoon showers and later flooded as the southwest monsoon advances. Farmers dry sow the autumn rice so they can harvest it early and immediately transplant the winter rice, which depends on the meager and erratic northeast monsoon rains. The autumn rice crop is subjected to two major stresses: drought

during initial growth stages and weeds. A few semidwarf rices withstand some drought but they are more prone to smothering by weeds than are the local tall varieties. Farmers prefer tall, nonlodging rice with a lush canopy of leaves. But the present tall cultivars lodge, even before panicle emergence, and suffer severe yield losses.

Preliminary investigations indicated the adaptability for dry sowing of some elite International Rice Yield Nursery (IRYN) rices of intermediate stature.

Among the rices in the Assam Rice Collection, the accession ARC 11775 has been identified as drought tolerant, tall, nonlodging, and fertilizer responsive, with a high degree of blast resistance. Its seed-to-seed growth duration is 105 to 110 days vs. 130 to 135 days for the

Characteristics of ARC 11775 a promising cultivar for rainfed lowlands, and a tall local variety. Kerala, India.

Variety	Growth duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield (kg/day)	Kernel color
ARC 11775	106	2.5	26.6	White
Ptb 26 (local tall indica)	135	1.8	13.0	Red

most popular tall varieties (See table).

The yield per day of ARC 11775 is double that of the all local variety now grown. Earliness without yield loss is desirable for autumn rice so that popular winter rices can be transplanted earlier in rainfed paddies.

Suakoko 8 — a new rice variety recommended for iron-toxic swamps in Liberia

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Rice varieties with genetic tolerance to iron toxicity are considered useful in many inland valley swamps in Liberia, where symptoms of the disorder develop in most rice crops. Gissi 27, a local variety recommended for deep waterlogged swamps, is tolerant of iron toxicity. But being tall, photoperiod sensitive, and late maturing (165 – 170 days), it cannot be used for double-cropping or for high-technology rice cultivation. IR5 is recommended for inland valley swamps, but it is susceptible to iron toxicity, which reduces its yields by as much as 40%.

More than 3,000 rice varieties have been screened and tested during the past 4 years at the Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko. Emphasis has been on varietal tolerance for iron toxicity in inland swamps. The most significant result is the selection of the line 2526 (Siam 25/Malunja³), which is tolerant of iron toxicity and has been named Suakoko 8 by the Liberian Ministry of Agriculture.

In trials across the country during the past 3 years, Suakoko 8 outyielded IR5 by about 20% in iron-toxic swamps. Under nontoxic conditions, IR5 and Suakoko 8 yield similarly but farmers in various parts of Liberia prefer Suakoko 8 because it has better cooking quality and is more palatable.

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